

Effect of Additives on the Conductance Behaviour of Iron and Cobalt Caprylate Solutions in *n*-Butanol

R. P. VARMA and H. K. BHARGAVA*

Department of Chemistry, D. A. V. College, Muzaffarnagar 251 001

Manuscript received 16 May 1977, revised 9 November 1977, accepted 12 March 1979

The effect of additives (water, ethylene glycol and aniline) on the conductivity of iron and cobalt caprylate solutions in *n*-butanol at 35° has been studied. The critical micelle concentrations of these soaps increase with increasing amount of water and ethylene glycol but it is independent of aniline concentration. The conductance behaviour of soap solutions in presence of additives is exhibited by a relationship: $\log \lambda = A + B \log C$, where A and B are constants and C is the concentration of soap in moles/litre. The constants A and B vary similarly in water and ethylene glycol but show a different behaviour in presence of aniline. The values of dissociation constant, K decrease and λ_{∞} increase with the addition of water and ethylene glycol but it shows a reverse behaviour in the presence of aniline.

THE formation of aggregates in non-aqueous solutions of surface active agents was early recognised¹⁻⁵ but there are many systems where the change in CMC as a function of the amounts of various additives are not yet known. The CMC change gives us information of the effect of additives on the surface activity and provides a clearer understanding of the action of surface active agents. It also affords information on the role of additives in concentrated solutions. The effect of *n*-propanol, iso-propanol and propionic acid on the conductivity of aqueous soap solutions was studied by Flockhart and Ubbelohde⁶ and it was suggested that these additives lower the CMC when added in small amounts. Bose and co-worker⁷⁻⁹ studied the conductance behaviour of sodium soap solution in presence of varying amounts of different alcohols. The effect of cyclohexane, *n*-heptane and toluene on the CMC of dodecylammonium chloride¹⁰ and benzene on potassium dodecyl sulphate¹¹ was measured. A considerable effect of small amounts of water or free fatty acids on the size, shape and CMC of surface active agents in non-aqueous solution was observed¹²⁻¹⁴.

In the present work, we attempted to study the effect of additives (water, ethylene glycol and aniline) on the conductance behaviour of iron and cobalt caprylate solutions in *n*-butanol by determining CMC, dissociation constant, K and molecular conductivity at infinite dilution, λ_{∞} and tried to establish $\lambda-C$ relationship in presence of these additives.

Experimental

Merck or B. D. H. reagent grade chemicals were used. Soaps were prepared in a manner described

previously¹⁵. Conductivity water was prepared in a glass apparatus, and in all cases freshly distilled water (alkaline potassium permanganate) was taken. The organic additives were distilled before use.

The procedure and apparatus used for the measurement of the conductivity of soap solutions were the same as reported earlier¹⁶. The reproducibility of the experimental data was examined by repeating the measurement several times. The reproducibility of the results was 0.1%.

Results and Discussion

Specific conductivity of iron and cobalt caprylates in butanol increases with increasing amount of water and ethylene glycol but shows the reverse behaviour in presence of varying amounts of aniline. The plots of specific conductivity *vs.* concentration of soap solution (Fig. 1) in presence of varying amounts of additives indicate an abrupt change at CMC. The values of CMC increase with increasing amount of water and ethylene glycol which is due to the solvent power of the mixture¹⁷. From the plots of CMC *vs.* amount of additive (Fig. 2 a and b) it is found that the CMC of iron caprylate solution increases rapidly up to $4.4 \times 10^{-3} M$ and then linearly but slowly with further addition of water whereas it increases linearly with increasing amount of ethylene glycol. The CMC of cobalt caprylate solution increases linearly with increasing amount of water but shows an intersection of two straight lines at $3.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ in presence of ethylene glycol. It has been observed that aniline as an additive does not affect the CMC of both the soaps.

* Chemistry Department, K. K. Jain Degree College, Khatauli (Muzaffarnagar) 251201.

Fig. 1. Plot of specific conductivity vs. soap concentration of cobalt caprylate in *n*-butanol in the presence of varying amounts of water.

Fig. 2(b) Plots of CMC vs. amount of ethylene glycol added to the soap solutions in *n*-butanol.

The plot (Fig. 3) of $\log \lambda$ vs. $\log C$ in presence of varying amounts of additives shows a linear relationship.

$$\log \lambda = A + B \log C \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where A and B are constants and C is the concentration of soap in moles/litre.

Fig. 2(a) Plots of CMC vs. amount of water added to the soap solutions in *n*-butanol.

Fig. 3 Plot of $\log \lambda$ vs. $\log C$ of iron caprylate solution in *n*-butanol in presence of varying amounts of ethylene glycol.

The values of A (Table 1) for the soap solutions decrease with increasing amount of aniline but increase in presence of other additives. The values of A for iron soap is greater than cobalt soap. Constant B (Table 2) varies with the increasing

amount of additive up to certain concentration and remain constant with further increasing additive concentration. It is found that the values of B in presence of water and ethylene glycol in *n*-butanol are lower than the values in pure *n*-butanol.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF CONSTANT A OF IRON AND COBALT SOAPS IN *n*-BUTANOL IN THE PRESENCE OF VARYING AMOUNTS (moles litre⁻¹) OF ADDITIVE

Water		Ethylene glycol		Aniline	
Amount × 10 ³	A	Amount × 10 ³	A	Amount × 10 ³	A
<i>Iron caprylate</i>					
1.10	-0.07	0.36	-0.38	0.23	-0.57
2.20	-0.06	0.72	-0.37	0.46	-0.59
3.31	-0.04	1.07	-0.36	0.69	-0.61
4.41	-0.02	1.43	-0.35	0.92	-0.61
5.52	0.01	1.79	-0.33	1.14	-0.67
6.62	0.02	2.15	-0.32	1.37	-0.69
<i>Cobalt caprylate</i>					
1.10	-0.95	0.89	-0.90	0.57	-1.70
3.31	-0.54	1.79	-0.85	1.15	-1.74
5.52	-0.13	2.69	-0.81	1.72	-1.82
6.62	-0.03	3.58	-0.71	2.30	-1.85
8.83	0.08	4.48	-0.67	2.87	-1.92
11.04	0.14	5.38	-0.64	3.44	-1.96

TABLE 2—VALUES OF CONSTANT B OF IRON AND COBALT SOAPS IN *n*-BUTANOL IN THE PRESENCE OF VARYING AMOUNTS (moles litre⁻¹) OF ADDITIVE

Water		Ethylene glycol		Aniline	
Amount × 10 ³	Constant B	Amount × 10 ³	Constant B	Amount × 10 ³	Constant B
<i>Iron caprylate</i>					
1.10	0.18	0.36	0.26	0.23	0.30
2.20	0.22	0.72	0.28	0.46	0.30
3.31	0.24	1.07	0.30	0.69	0.30
4.41	0.25	1.43	0.30	0.92	0.30
5.52	0.26	1.79	0.30	1.14	0.30
6.62	0.26	2.15	0.30	1.37	0.30
<i>Cobalt caprylate</i>					
1.10	0.36	0.89	0.38	0.57	0.56
3.31	0.30	1.79	0.42	1.15	0.56
5.52	0.24	2.69	0.44	1.72	0.56
6.62	0.24	3.58	0.44	2.30	0.56
8.83	0.24	4.48	0.44	2.87	0.56
11.04	0.24	5.38	0.44	3.44	0.56

Since the soap behaves as a weak electrolyte in dilute solutions, an expression¹⁸ can be derived for the dissociation of iron and cobalt soaps. If α is the degree of dissociation of cobalt soap, the dissociation constant, K is given by the relation

$$K = \frac{4C^2\alpha^2}{1-\alpha} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

Since α of soaps in dilute solution is very small, ionic concentration will be low and therefore inter-ionic effects will be almost negligible. Such solution, therefore, do not deviate appreciably from ideal behaviour and hence the activities of the ions are almost equal to concentrations. On substituting

the value of α defined by λ/λ_∞ in equation (ii) one obtains

$$C^2\lambda^2 = \frac{K\lambda_\infty^2}{4\lambda} - \frac{K\lambda_\infty^2}{4} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

Similarly for iron soaps the following expression can be derived :

$$C^2\lambda^2 = \frac{K\lambda_\infty^2}{27\lambda} - \frac{K\lambda_\infty^2}{27} \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

The plots of $C^2\lambda^2$ vs. $1/\lambda$ for cobalt soap and $C^2\lambda^2$ vs. $1/\lambda$ for iron soap are linear below CMC and the equations fail above this concentration. The values of dissociation constant, K and molecular conductivity at infinite dilution, λ_∞ of soaps in presence of varying amounts of additives have been obtained from the intercepts and slopes of the linear plots. It is evident from the Tables 3 and 4 that the values of K decrease and λ_∞ increase with increasing amount of water and ethylene glycol but these parameters show a reverse trend in presence of aniline.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF DISSOCIATION CONSTANT, K FOR IRON AND COBALT SOAPS IN *n*-BUTANOL IN THE PRESENCE OF VARYING AMOUNTS OF ADDITIVE

Water		Ethylene glycol		Aniline	
Amount × 10 ³	K × 10 ⁵	Amount × 10 ³	K × 10 ⁵	Amount × 10 ³	K × 10 ⁵
<i>Iron caprylate</i>					
1.10	1.592	0.36	3.226	0.23	1.165
2.20	1.041	0.72	1.215	0.46	3.684
3.31	0.690	1.07	0.831	0.69	4.984
4.41	0.532	1.43	0.650	0.92	5.793
5.52	0.494	1.79	0.590	1.14	5.923
6.62	0.438	2.15	0.537	1.37	6.415
<i>Cobalt caprylate</i>					
1.10	23.450	0.89	1.873	0.57	2.623
3.31	21.123	1.79	1.475	1.15	3.800
5.52	19.456	2.69	1.187	1.72	5.713
6.62	16.718	3.58	0.946	2.30	6.925
8.83	13.233	4.48	0.646	2.87	8.220
11.04	9.529	5.38	0.486	3.44	9.950

TABLE 4—VALUES OF MOLECULAR CONDUCTIVITY AT INFINITE DILUTION, λ_∞ OF IRON AND COBALT SOAPS IN *n*-BUTANOL IN THE PRESENCE OF VARYING AMOUNTS (moles litre⁻¹) OF ADDITIVE

Water		Ethylene glycol		Aniline	
Amount × 10 ³	λ_∞	Amount × 10 ³	λ_∞	Amount × 10 ³	λ_∞
<i>Iron caprylate</i>					
1.10	2.500	0.36	2.166	0.23	1.951
2.20	3.888	0.72	3.076	0.46	1.794
3.31	4.324	1.07	3.571	0.69	1.600
4.41	4.545	1.43	4.026	0.92	1.470
5.52	4.571	1.79	4.121	1.14	1.454
6.62	5.116	2.15	4.457	1.37	1.488
<i>Cobalt caprylate</i>					
1.10	1.800	0.89	1.702	0.57	1.562
3.31	2.000	1.79	1.951	1.15	1.214
5.52	3.390	2.69	2.102	1.72	0.916
6.62	4.975	3.58	2.372	2.30	0.888
8.83	5.142	4.48	2.409	2.87	0.867
11.04	6.315	5.38	2.652	3.44	0.750

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. K. N. Mehrotra, Reader in Chemistry Department, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur for his keen interest in the work and the college authorities for providing laboratory facilities.

References

1. L. KAHLBERG, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1902, **6**, 1.
2. B. C. SOYENKOFF, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 2519.
3. C. J. BONER, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1935, **27**, 665.
4. S. B. ELLIOTT, "The Alkaline Earth and Heavy Metal Soaps", Reinhold, New York, 1946, p. 53.
5. H. R. BAKER, D. T. JONES and W. A. ZISMAN, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1949, **41**, 137.
6. B. D. FLOCKHART and A. R. UBBELOHDE, *J. Colloid. Sci.*, 1953, **8**, 428.
7. A. N. BOSE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 135; *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1954, **203**, 119; 1955, **204**, 16.
8. A. N. BOSE and J. MISRA, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1954, **137**, 37.
9. A. N. BOSE and K. N. MEHROTRA, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1958, **158**, 39.
10. E. HUTCHINSON, A. INABA and L. G. BAILEY, *Z. Physik. Chem. (Frankfurt)*, 1955, **5**, 344.
11. W. LIN, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1955, **28**, 227.
12. P. DEBYE and W. PRINS, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1958, **13**, 86.
13. J. G. HONIG and C. R. SINGLETERRY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 201.
14. J. G. HONIG and C. R. SINGLETERRY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 1108.
15. R. P. VARMA and H. K. BHARGAVA, *Roczniki Chemii, Ann. Soc. Chim., Polonorum.*, 1976, **50**, 307.
16. R. P. VARMA and P. BAHADUR, *Cellulose Chem. Technol.*, 1974, **8**, 27.
17. S. MIYAGISHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1975, **48(8)**, 2349.
18. G. A. KRAUS and W. C. BRAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **35**, 1315.